

Deliverable Report - Benchmarking

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Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC)

Building the foundation for Norway's AI sovereignty with Compute and Competence

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Deliverables final report

D9.5 Document and empirically evaluate infrastructure

Glossary of Terms

Term	Description
Apptainer / Singularity	Containerization platforms generally preferred in HPC systems, utilized by the framework to allow reproducible software environments.
Docker	A containerization platform supported by naic-bench to provide reproducible software environments and simplified workflows for executing benchmarks.
eX3	A heterogeneous, experimental computing infrastructure hosted at Simula, consisting of a variety of compute nodes used for benchmarking GPU performance.
fp16 / fp32	Floating point precision formats (16-bit and 32-bit) used as testing parameters during the execution of machine learning workloads.
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit, an accelerator hardware component utilized to improve the performance of ML/AI-based workloads.
ML/AI MLCommons	Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence. An ongoing community attempt to provide a standardized methodology, data sets, and workloads for assessing different aspects of ML/AI applications.
naic-bench	A new, extensible Python-based benchmarking framework created to allow benchmarking to be carried out easily and in a reproducible manner by normal users.
PyTorch	An ML/AI application framework that uses the concept of an 'accelerator' and software abstractions to allow the vendor-agnostic training of machine learning models.
SLURM	A job scheduler used to organize the execution of naic-bench across compute nodes in a cluster environment.
YAML	A data serialization format used to define the single point of configuration per benchmark, making re-parametrization easier and more maintainable.

1. Executive Summary

This report details efforts to document and empirically evaluate an existing computing infrastructure. In this context, we focused on benchmarking GPU performance for ML/AI workloads, primarily using the available hardware on eX3, an experimental computing infrastructure hosted at Simula.

The current rise of AI-based applications has created significant demands for using GPUs to improve performance of AI-based workloads. The GPU market is, however, dominated by a few vendors, Nvidia, AMD and Intel, where Nvidia is clearly the main supplier. Benchmarking can be used as a tool to compare hardware across vendors and to allow better decision-making for hardware provisioning.

We first investigated existing benchmarking approaches, concluding that they are not currently well suited to evaluating existing computing infrastructures. This is partly due to shortcomings in terms of portability and reproducibility of the benchmarks. We therefore created a new, extensible benchmarking framework to overcome these limitations. The new framework, called *naic-bench*, currently offers a curated collection of ML/AI workloads, but it is not limited to such workloads and can be extended to other application domains in the future. The current set of ML/AI applications are based on common, vendor-specific reference implementations (by Nvidia) of state-of-the-art training approaches.

There have been significant efforts from the MLCommons community to increase transparency on GPU performance for training and inference. Meanwhile, vendors themselves typically provide their optimally tweaked implementations, often requiring admin level access to system. This makes the reproduction of benchmarking approaches difficult, or at least limits it to a small group of actors.

The *naic-bench* framework allows benchmarking to be carried out more easily and in a reproducible manner by normal users. We achieve this by providing publicly accessible containers with reproducible software environments for the benchmark applications. In addition, we take advantage of the latest developments in ML/AI application frameworks. In particular, PyTorch has introduced the concept of ‘accelerator’ and corresponding software abstractions. This allows training of machine learning models to be done in a vendor-agnostic way.

With a large, continuously updated software stack, it becomes increasingly important to simplify benchmarking procedures. These efforts provide a foundation for regular site-testing, i.e., to identify how system performance evolves after updates in the software toolchain. Hence, *naic-bench* becomes not only a tool for initial characterization of hardware, but over the full life cycle of a computing infrastructure.

2. Detailed Progress by Activity

State of the Art: MLCommons

The MLCommons group is an ongoing attempt to provide a standardized methodology, data sets and workloads for assessing different aspects of ML/AI applications. It is an often given reference for benchmarks (cf. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.01500>) with the aim of facilitating reuse and replicability of results. The process to do this is, however, not well documented, and was at the time of investigation not easily executable.

The general MLCommons approach is to provide reference implementations for a set of benchmarks (see, e.g., https://github.com/mlcommons/training/tree/master/object_detection), and then announce and execute benchmark rounds in which industrial contributors implement the reference benchmarks for their system and report the results including logs for verification. This process permits industrial partners to perform elaborate fine-tunings while benchmarking their hardware, providing an indication of the best possible performance for a given workload and system. Results of the benchmarking rounds are made publicly available on <https://github.com/mlcommons/> in repositories `training_results_vX.X` for X.X with v5.1 being the latest completed round, and latest open call being v6.0.

Motivation

Although we first considered employing the reference benchmarks supplied by MLCommons, we decided against doing so after encountering practical issues. During our investigation and efforts to reproduce results, we encountered bugs that had been identified during the previous benchmark rounds, but were still not fixed. We also observed that open issues had a low response or resolution rate, leading to uncertainty about when or whether they might be addressed. Performing benchmarking correctly can be challenging in itself (cf. <https://hstor.inf.ethz.ch/publications/img/hoeffler-12-ways-data-science-preprint.pdf>), but here, replicating the vendor-specific implementations turned out to be additionally complex. Especially since benchmarks are carried out by the vendor on own computing infrastructures. In particular, it is assumed that superuser privileges are readily available on these machines. As a consequence, there is a high bar for running the benchmarks, and only system administrators will be able to do so in practice on typical clusters. As a result, we aimed to measure ‘typical’ performance (for medium experienced users) in contrast to ‘maximum’ achievable performance under ideal conditions, i.e., only be achievable setup that requires a deep knowledge of the hardware and software configuration options.

Developing an extensible framework for ML/AI benchmarking

After identifying limitations of the MLCommons benchmarks, further investigations led to another set of benchmark applications, namely *Nvidia’s Deep Learning Examples*. The cloud provider lambda.ai uses Nvidia’s examples as basis for benchmarking GPUs across their portfolio range. Since the results from Nvidia’s Deep Learning Examples and lambda.ai are publicly available, we replicated the benchmarking approach and extended it to include additional hardware vendors, such as AMD and Intel.

The figure below displays benchmark results for a set of machine learning workloads on a variety of NVIDIA and AMD GPUs from the eX3 cluster.

Figure 1: Benchmarking results for single GPU

Expanding the testing spectrum to cover various vendors, up to four GPUs, floating point precision fp16 and fp32, leads to a significantly larger result set:

The development of *naic-bench* was done in in three main stages:

- (1) Replicate the lambda.ai approach on the available set of Nvidia hardware (on eX3) and ensure comparable results.
- (2) Extend the approach to new accelerators from AMD (RTX and MI Instinct Series) and Intel (Gaudi Series).

Figure 2: Benchmarking across parameter range

(3) Improve the usability and reproducibility by providing a unified software framework and tools for carrying out benchmarks.

We succeeded to replicate the lambda.ai results, thus completing the first stage, based on existing benchmarking software and tools provided by lambda.ai. However, during the second and third stages, it became apparent that major changes were needed to facilitate new vendors and accelerators, as well as to simplify the benchmarking procedure, from preparing data sets to collecting and post-processing results.

Meanwhile, working with the existing code base required the handling of parameters that were distributed across the codebase, thus making a re-parametrization cumbersome and less maintainable. As a result, we focused on a streamlining the approach to permit easier cross-vendor comparison, despite the fact that the actual results represent typical but not optimal performance, and thus can still be subject to improvement.

The efforts described above have culminated in the *naic-bench* framework. The framework provides tools for benchmarking a curated set of ML/AI workloads with several notable features:

- single point of access: one executable for setup and preparation of benchmarks
- single point of configuration: YAML-based configuration per benchmark
- extensibility: by loading runnable examples from external repositories
- containerization: support for Docker and Singularity/Apptainer to allow reproducible software environments and simplified workflows to execute benchmarks

These features are described in more detail below.

Single Point of Access The Python-based framework comes with several subcommands:

- **show**: List the available set of benchmarks.
- **prepare**: Download and prepare necessary data sets for a given benchmark.
- **run**: Execute a benchmark—a successful execution depends on further requirements, e.g., the availability of GPU drivers etc., *naic-bench* embeds limited options to prepare this environment but rather relies on the usage of predefined containers (see subcommands: *docker* and *singularity*)
- **report**: Collect benchmark results and generate a consistent report
- **docker**: Prepare Docker containers or execute a benchmark in a Docker container

- **singularity:** Prepare a Singularity/Apptainer container (based on a previously created Docker container) or execute a benchmark in a Singularity/Apptainer container

Single point of configuration Having a single point of configuration for benchmarks, permits an easier and more transparent handling of application specific parametrizations, also referred to as variants. For this purpose, we introduced a YAML-based configuration file for each benchmark. The configuration file describes where the source code for the benchmark can be obtained (e.g., a Git repository and a specific version), as well as preprocessing steps for preparing input data sets.

Additional instructions include:

- **command:** how to run the application are also specified in this configuration
- **metrics:** how to extract specific metrics from log files
- **batch_size:** automatic scaling of the batch_size, depending on the current size of the GPU to maximize memory usage
- **parametrization:** common configuration option, e.g., from command-line arguments, are injected using placeholders such as GPU_COUNT, DATA_DIR, or TMP_DIR

An example configuration file is shown below:

```
pytorch:
  gnmt:
    repo:
      url: https://github.com/2maz/naic-DeepLearningExamples.git
    prepare:
      data: gnmt.prepare
    command: >
      python train.py
    command_distributed: >
      python -m torch.distributed.run --nproc_per_node={{GPU_COUNT}} train.py
    metrics:
      throughput:
        pattern: "^. *Training:.*$"
        split_by: ' '
        match_group_index: 4
    variants:
      fp32:
        base_dir: PyTorch/Translation/GNMT
        batch_size:
          size_1gb:
            default: 8
            overrides:
              xpu: 10
          multiple_gpu_scaling_factor:
            default: 0.7
          apply_via: --train-batch-size
        arguments:
          dataset-dir: "{{DATA_DIR}}/gnmt/wmt16_de_en"
          math: fp32
          epochs: 2
          seed: 2
          train-loader-workers: "{{CPU_COUNT:<=32}}"
          save-dir: "{{TMP_DIR}}"
```

Extensibility A benchmark configuration is defined by the user and can be easily switched via a command-line argument: `--confd-dir`, which makes it possible to load benchmark from various

configuration folder / repositories. In combination with defining the application examples from git repositories, the benchmarking framework can be flexibly used.

Containerization Containers offer one approach to tackle reproducibility challenges. Although the use of containers has some drawbacks or limitations, many hardware vendors, including Nvidia, AMD and Intel, provide Docker-based containers for users to benefit from GPU support in the latest versions of Torch/PyTorch. These containers were used in *naic-bench* to carry out benchmarks on eX3. While eX3 permits the usage of Docker-containers, most HPC systems generally prefer to use Singularity/Apptainer-based containerization. To bridge the gap from Docker to Singularity images, we use the vendor-provided Docker images as a basis to create corresponding Singularity images.

The workflow to create a Singularity container from a Docker container has been embedded into *naic-bench*, so that users can take advantage of a streamlined containerization process. As a first step, a Docker-based image is created from a predefined recipe (which is included in *naic-bench*). The Docker container can be used to run interactively (e.g., by providing no additional arguments), or to run benchmarks through the *naic-bench* command:

```
$> naic-bench docker --data-dir data --
      naic-bench run
          --data-dir /data
          --benchmarks-dir benchmarks
          --gpu-count 1
          --device-type nvidia
          --output-base-dir /data/reports-ex3
          --recreate-venv
```

The interactive mode gives users more direct control over how experiments are run, while the above presented execution is used for SLURM script generation. Any docker image can be converted to a Singularity image, which can then be used to run benchmarks in a similar manner:

```
$> naic-bench singularity --data-dir data --
      naic-bench run
          --data-dir /data
          --benchmarks-dir benchmarks
          --gpu-count 1
          --device-type nvidia
          --output-base-dir /data/reports-ex3
          --recreate-venv
```

Cross-vendor support Support in *naic-bench* is available for the following device-types: nvidia, nvidia-volta, habana, xpu, rocm, and cpu, where the vendor to type mapping is given in the following table.

Vendor	Device Type
Nvidia	nvidia, nvidia-volta
AMD	rocm
Intel	habana, xpu

For each of the device types a `Dockerfile.devicetype` exists, which implements the recipe to build the Docker images. Note, that for Nvidia the user has to register and login as developer before a container can be pulled.

SLURM-based execution The experimental infrastructure eX3 is heterogeneous and consists of a variety of compute nodes, which is in sharp contrast to typical production HPC clusters. This permits benchmarks to be run on a variety of hardware configurations, but it also requires proper setup through the SLURM job scheduler. Hence, to organize the execution of *naic-bench* in a SLURM-based cluster, the framework comes with a template-based script generation for eX3. This capability can also be adapted to other clusters or environments in the future.

Job scripts are generated by invoking a shell script, which takes the node name, GPU count and type of GPU as parameters:

```
./slurm/ex3/naic-bench.sh <nodename> <gpu-count> <gpu-type>
```

The result is a node-specific SLURM job script based on an existing template.

3. Code

The latest version of the sourcecode is available on <https://github.com/2maz/naic-bench.git>. The latest release is also archived on Zenodo: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.19607454](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19607454)

4. Deviations

The initial target for the benchmarking activities aimed to include multi-GPU on multi-node benchmarks. While multi-GPU benchmarks have been carried out and benchmark results were collected, the multi-node benchmarks have not. During the benchmarking process, it became increasingly important to develop the benchmarking framework to support a wide spectrum of accelerator devices, CPU architectures (aarch64, x86_64), and application configurations (e.g., fp16, fp32, automatic mixed precision). Though we target mainly GPU benchmarking, we also evaluated the plain CPU performance using IBM PowerPC - which claims better support for AI workloads. The *naic-bench* framework still needs to be evaluated and possibly adapted to facilitate multi-node benchmarking.